

KILL OR CURE

(How Medical Doctors Can Harm Your Health)

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In my paper "UK Covid 19 Deaths in the Elderly" =[UKCDE] on page 4 it states that 23,700 people are killed in the UK as a result of the NHS medicines given to them. Hence on page 10 of that paper I asked the question, "How does a medication, supposed to cure, kill a patient?" I now may have part of the answer to this important question. The world needs to focus on the danger of modern pharmaceuticals. Man made dangerous chemistry.

Also in a UK review published in September 2021 led by England's chief pharmaceutical officer, Dr. Keith Ridge, the conclusions reached are as follows:-

(my comments in brackets)

"One in ten drugs (means medications or medicines) dispensed by GPs (general medical practitioners in the UK) and pharmacists are unnecessary and potentially harmful. Over-prescription is a serious problem with harmful consequences. The review states that 20% of all hospital admissions among people over 65 years old, are caused by the adverse effects of medicines. Also 6.5% of the total hospital admissions have the same cause. The more drugs a person takes the higher their risk of reacting badly to one of them. Around 15% of people take at least five medicines a day. The review also suggests that a remedy might be to prescribe non-clinical services called 'social prescribing' which may include such things as exercises or cooking classes."

Here we have a recognition that modern medicines do not always cure patients. Instead the review has found that many thousands of UK citizens are being harmed so much that they require a hospital admission to deal with the symptoms created by medicines, which were supposed to cure them of some condition. Many do die.

All doctors once made a promise - "**first do no harm**"; now obsolete it seems.

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Introduction

In my paper [UKCDE] mentioned above, I state that a university study published in 2018, nearly 24,000 people are killed every year in the UK directly or indirectly from the mistakes made prescribing modern NHS medicines. This is nearly 2,000 every month. It further estimates that 237 million prescriptions every year are dangerous. This is nearly 20 million every month of the year or 650,000 every day. And this is only in the UK, which has less than 1% of the worlds population. We can only guess how many people globally are killed by modern medicines every year - it could be many millions. And as for those not killed but severely harmed, it could be more than one billion people are harmed by medicine errors every year across the world. It appears that this important fact is not being addressed either by the World Health Organisation or any national health system. How have pharmaceutical companies put us all into the grip of death? Are they more concerned with making money from chemistry experiments than curing sickness?

The numbers above could be compared to the 1,300,000 people annually killed on the roads across the world due to accidents of one kind or another. Also the average of people

killed in airplane accidents in the last 10 years is about 360 per year across the world. I would say that it is much more important to open up the reason for deaths due to medicines; since cars and airplanes are only meant to transport us, whereas medicines are supposed to make us well from sickness, not kill us in the process.

Causes of Modern Medicines Being Harmful

For many centuries, maybe thousands of years, it has been known by the human race that the human body has a great capacity to mend itself, resist pathogens (moulds, viruses or bacteria), hence to cure itself of disease. It is relatively recent that medical people have been amazed at the capacity of the human immune system in this respect. This is the beginning of them catching up with those people of ancient times. The main error of modern medication systems is to generally ignore this capacity of the human metabolism to cure the body, and instead to introduce a powerful chemistry to try to take over the healing functions of the human body. It is this chemistry (modern medicine) which is alien to the human metabolism. It suppresses the natural chemistry and acts indiscriminately throughout the body by entering into the blood stream and causing damage to organs and the body's own systems of curing. In many cases the human immune system is damaged or suppressed by the medication. This is the fundamental error – using alien chemistry to try and to do what Mother Nature can do very well, if given the chance.

The alien nature of the medication is borne out by the fact that our body chemistry rejects the medicine chemistry within about 4 hours or so. Necessitating more pills or tablets to be taken at regular intervals, so as to keep the medical chemistry doing its work. This puts the body under constant attack from the chemistry of the medication.

What is not realised by modern medics is that the natural defence and repair systems of the human body can either go to sleep, or can be suppressed by the various matters which make up our lifestyle behaviour; alcohol, smoking, junk food, lack of exercise etc.

If this were realised then medics would understand what the doctors of the past were doing, when they used natural plant parts or extracts to wake up the human systems. Natural medicines do not necessarily always try to effect a cure, in many cases they simply wake up or strengthen existing systems in the body, so that it can cure itself. This is far different from trying to do the job with externally applied chemistry and damaging the human metabolism in the act. Man made chemistry is inferior to that of Mother Nature.

The powerful chemistry of many modern medicines is damaging to the human body. Look at the list inside any medicine package and see what side effects (symptoms or illnesses) are listed from the clinical trials for the medicine. These are confessed known effects of the medicine. Most people do not read these and if they do, they do not realise the significance of the information. It means they are taking a poison. Proof of the damaging effect of modern medicine is shown in the fact that approximately 50% of all medication courses in the UK are halted due to unacceptable side effects – meaning damage to the person's organs and internal systems. Sometimes this damage can be irreversible. Hence ceasing the medication may not stop the side effects occurring.

On the contrary there are thousands of plant or other natural medicines that have been and are being used across the whole world. By comparison with modern medications they have very few, if any, side effects. Overdosing of plant medicines is rarely harmful. Almost all modern man made medicines can cause severe sickness and even death if an overdose is administered. The common over-the-counter pain killer paracetamol will kill a person if an overdose is taken, due to causing severe liver damage. These facts are proof, if needed, that they are harmful. Yet valerian, a natural pain reliever, can deal with most common pains with no side effects; also overdosing it will not be harmful.

All clinical trials on modern medicines are, through necessity, conducted in isolation to any other modern medicine. Also they are trialled on patients with only one ailment; meaning they are not taking any other medication during the trial. Yet when used in practise with sick patients, they may be administered along with other medications taken for another health condition (see above "15% of people take 5 medicines"). Hence the side effects of the trial may be irrelevant, since the side effects of the medication are unknown when taken in combination with another strong chemistry; or when the patient has more than one ailment. This is part of the answer to how medicines can cause harm or indeed kill.

Above are some of the causes of damage to health from modern medicine.

The Human Body Fighting Back

Another important fact, which is not realised by modern medics, is the capability of the human body to mask the harmful effects of alien chemistry. This is noticed by those who take up, for the first time, smoking tobacco, drinking alcohol or taking hallucinatory drugs. The first intake of any of these things will have a very strong effect on the person. Dizziness, sickness or other strong symptoms caused by the poisonous effect of the substance taken. These effects become less in time as the person continues to administer the poisonous chemistry. How can that be? Simply it is the human body producing another chemistry to counter or mask the effect of the poison. This counter chemistry is another poison produced within the body. But because it is designed by the human body to eliminate an externally administered poison, the two cancel each other to some extent; but not 100%. This is an example of the human system's ability to cure or counteract foreign harmful substances coming from without. Yet in many cases harm is slowly building up from the two poisons remaining in the bloodstream.

The fact of this internal counter poison is noticed by smokers and drug addicts and alcoholics when they attempt to stop taking the previous substance. They get what is known as "withdrawal symptoms". These are caused by the patient's own body, because it continues the habit of producing the counter chemistry for the previously regularly administered substance. But because there is no administered poison to cancel out the body's own poison, the patient suffers from a poison made within the body. In time, if the withdrawal is managed correctly, then the body stops producing the counter poison and the symptoms will abate. But some harm may remain within vital organs of the body.

If we can understand this, we can soon see that when side effects from a modern drug or medicine begin to occur, a doctor may say, "These may go away after a while." If they do go, it does not mean that the effect on the body has stopped. Instead the chemistry of the patient has begun to produce another poison to cancel out or mask the effect of the medicine poison. Then the patient has two poisons constantly in the blood stream.

Alternatives to Administering Harmful Medicines

The above masking or production of internal counter poisons does not happen with plant medicines, because the chemistry is not so alien to the human body. This comes about because we all eat plants as food. Nature has produced only very few plants which are rejected or cause illness to the human body. Hence plant medicines only have positive effects on the human chemistry, and do not produce harmful effects or the need to produce a counter poison. Herbalists know the harmful plants and do not use them.

A person regularly taking modern pharmaceuticals is slowly shortening their life. This is happening because the side effects may have abated, but are continuing under cover of their body's ability to mask the side effect with another poison.

A statement made in 2017 by UK National Health researchers studying the over-prescription of modern medicines was that, "*Many normal patients are moving from the*

kingdom of the well into the kingdom of the sick". Which means a permanent loss of their normal health situation. This is happening because all the organs and systems in the patients body are slowly becoming weakened or damaged; resulting in death earlier than it would be naturally. Plant medicines do not have this effect.

The attempt by modern pharmaceuticals to cure human illness has failed for the above reasons. They are only shortening the life of patients and at great cost. They rarely return a patient to full health where no medicine is required. Which is what natural medicines do in the majority of cases. We need to restore normal health not lose it.

Another fact in most cases is that modern medicines aim to alleviate symptoms of a condition; not necessarily to remove the cause or cure the patient. This being so in some cases the patient needs to take the medicine for a long time. Pharmaceutical companies are happy if their products need to be used for longer. Herbal medicine aims to remove the cause and restore the normal health of the body's systems. Herbalists are not rich.

This scenario of causing harm can be avoided by the use of plant or natural substances to assist the human body to effect a remedy for common illnesses and many rare diseases. Knowledge of which plants help with which ailments is very widely known. And to be fair, many national medical system across the world do use them to treat their populations. Hence this paper is not so much directed to them, only for the degree to which they use modern pharmaceuticals instead of natural plant based medicines.

Getting the Correct Medicine for the Job

Modern medical diagnosis is lacking in co-ordination. Many ordinary doctors have not either been fully trained in it; or they have not woken up to its importance. Incorrect diagnosis leads inevitably to the incorrect remedy. This may create a serious time delay causing the patient's illness to move to a more advanced stage or complexity.

Incorrect diagnosis is an important part of the cause of harm or lack of cure to patients. This can happen whichever medication system is used. Hence correct diagnosis is important. It is in fact more important than which medicine to use. As with lack of knowledge in the use of plant medicines, there is also lack of knowledge about natural systems of diagnosis. The magic of Mother Nature has given us systems for diagnosis.

A good example is the human eye, which is more than just a sense organ. It is actually an extension of the human brain which we can interrogate. There are hundreds of tiny nerve paths leading from the brain into each filament of the iris of the human eye. These fine nerves originate from many parts of the human brain. They are not connected with the sense of sight, instead carry information about the various organs which report their condition to those many areas of the brain. Hence the iris becomes a map of the current condition of the many organs and parts of the human body. This science has been called iridology; the science of the human iris; carried out by iridologists.

Consider the picture to the right of a human eye. The hundreds of filaments within the iris are clearly visible. Close examination will show that some filaments have clumping or different colours within them. Each of these differences carries a meaning for the iridologist. If this is the right eye of the patient the left one will show other differences. These will be due to the various left and right aspects of the patients body. For example, left lung or left kidney. Right lung or right kidney etc. etc. The experienced iridologists becomes capable of interpreting these signs.

Ancient civilisations all studied the human eye for medical reasons. The Chaldeans and the Egyptians both left clay tablets or ceramics with details of the human iris on them,

which appear to be associated with medicine. It is certain that their medical knowledge was handed down mainly by oral tradition. Hence we have a few writings on medicines but none on iridology. The Eber's Egyptian papyrus and others give information from 7,000 years ago on medicines, but there is little or no information about the vital subject of diagnosis. The Eber's papyrus gives information on ailments for every part of the human body and their symptoms. There is also information on administering more than 700 herbs. But any knowledge of iridology for diagnosis seems to have been lost.

Nearer to our times the Greeks left some information in the Hippocratic writings that the condition of the human iris was an indication of specific disease or conditions. And it maybe that because the Greeks occupied Egypt prior to the collapse of the ancient Egyptian dynasties, that Greek physicians obtained some of the oral tradition related to the human iris diagnosis system. This we can only infer because little evidence remains.

In both the 18th and 19th centuries Europeans have looked closer at the relationship between markings in the iris and the health of the patient. The most remarkable of these began a process which has lead to the modern understanding of iris diagnosis. And I have positive personal evidence that it works. This short story is also evidence that herbal medicine works in place of conventional modern medicine or surgery.

In the 1970s I was stricken with a severe case of haemorrhoids (piles). The case was so severe that when a colonic camera examination was being undertaken in hospital, the doctor explained the severity and asked me if some medical students could come to view the camera images of the inside of my colon. I agreed; and the ensuing comments I heard were evidence to me that the haemorrhoids were indeed extensive and large. The doctor recommended surgery to remove them and duly put me on the waiting list.

However, my wife had previously had success with a herbalist for her life long suffering with cystitis, which was causing her great discomfort during the pregnancy with our first child. So she said to me, "Why don't you give him a try and see what he has to say?" So I made an appointment with the first herbalist's diagnosis in my life in 1971.

This herbalists had spent more than 12 years in Tibet, learning from monks and other medical people all they knew about the various means to cure human ailments. He cured my wife's cystitis of more than 30 years duration, in a very short time and it has never come back in 50 years. When I went to him and explained my plight, he picked up a large magnifying device and looked closely into my eyes. After making a few notes he said, "You have slight sclerosis of the liver and a restriction in your portal vein which has caused the blood flow returning to the liver to be impeded. This is the cause of the extended veins. I will first treat the liver and the portal vein, then move on to shrink the veins back to their normal size." I was amazed at how quick he was able to pin point the problem, and with great confidence in his voice, to spell out the process of the cure. This diagnosis he did with no other physical examination, only looking at my irises. He told me it was called iris diagnosis.

After one month taking his medicine I returned. Looking into my eyes again he then made more notes and said that the first stage was successful. After another month of a different medicine I returned again and he said that the haemorrhoids had vanished.

I did feel that this was the case. But a confirmation from another source is always a good thing, when you are not sure. This came from the same doctor who had recommended surgery. I was called by the hospital to go in for the surgery about one month after the herbal treatment. I contacted the original doctor and said that I thought the problem had gone away. He called me in for another examination. With the same camera he had a good look; he agreed that there were no haemorrhoids. He asked me how it could have happened? But because I knew that herbalists are not recognised in the UK

NHS system, I simply said that I had taken on a high fibre diet, which seemed to do the trick. He congratulated me with the success and said, "Keep on with the high fibre".

Above I have taken some space to demonstrate two points. Firstly that iris diagnosis can be helpful in addition or instead of physical or internal examination. Also that the condition can be dealt with using plant medicines. We should also note here; the proposed surgery was only to deal with the symptoms or the effect of a condition, but not the cause. In the interim between being put on a hospital waiting list and the final outcome, I found out from many people that after surgery haemorrhoids often return. This maybe because only the symptoms have been treated not the cause. This shows another reason why correct diagnosis is important; leading to the correct treatment. I should mention here that the haemorrhoids have not returned in more than 50 years.

Iris diagnosis was greatly enhanced in the 19th century in Europe by a young man with an ailing owl. Ignatz von Peczely a young Hungarian boy had a pet owl. The owl broke a leg. Ignatz noticed that a black line formed in the owls iris on the same side as the broken leg. Gradually as the leg healed he noticed that the black line faded; and was gone when the leg was back to normal. This young man later worked in a hospital and requested permission to list peoples illnesses and to make observations of their irises. After some years he was able to collate the information and relate iris markings to specific illnesses and conditions. These observations lead to other doctors doing similar research.

Now in this 21st century there is a vast amount of collated information assisting medical people to make accurate diagnosis of almost every adverse health condition; simply by looking into the irises of the patient. Yet it seems that officially the jury is still out on this method. Although I have experience that a talented herbalists was good at it, not all those who dabble with it have had success. As with all medical things we find that every patient reacts differently to treatments. It may be that the irises of each person do not always show up defects in various parts of the body in the same way. Hence as well as looking at the iris it is also necessary to know more about the individual patient's eyes.

I am sure that iris diagnosis can be of value. The herbalist who treated my wife for cystitis did look into her irises. He asked her about her right kidney; if she had any problem in the past with it? Many years previously she did have a kidney infection. He stated that he could see that scars still remained in the right kidney. So there must be some value in this method if he could get that information simply by looking at her irises.

Iridology needs to be studied correctly and practised for a long time before the physician can be confident with it. Of course symptom study is also good diagnosis.

It may be that hospitals need to have one or two people who have the job of only dealing with diagnosis. If they were well trained in iridology, they may get vast experience of seeing a great number of irises related to a wide range of conditions. This may be able to overcome the discrepancies which have arisen in the past with iridology; which has put it on the back burner for most normal health systems. It is these discrepancies which have deterred medics from using the iridology diagnosis system.

The process of recording and deciphering the wide range of discolourings and markings found in the human iris is complex and needs deep study. But if eventually it leads to correct or confirmed diagnosis then the correct medicine can be prescribed. Many cases of harm arise from incorrect diagnosis. With modern poisonous medicines this is one of the major factors in death or other harm to patients.

With herbal medicines there would be little or no harm. Eventually the correct herb can be found and the condition eliminated. Therefore maximum effort is required in the art of diagnosis.

One set of diagrams of the left and right irises is shown below. But readers should be aware that there are many of these with some variations. Also the top yellow areas must be considered suspect as some relate to the difficult subject of the human mind.

In 2017 I followed a course on Iridology by The School of Natural Health Sciences, and I can verify from observations made into irises with a special camera, taken from my own and some from my family members, that there are definite signs in the irises which correlate to the above diagrams. These were also related to the areas indicated on the diagrams above and the symptoms in the person at the time. So there is value in diagnosis with Iridology. My small experience with it has shown that it is complex and needs time.

Human Blindness About Man-made Chemistry

Above I have put forward a case that alien chemistry produced in laboratories is causing harm and early death to many patients. There is much evidence that this is known in various circles; some of these are in the Appendix below taken from my paper UKCDE. But here I would like to put forward further evidence of both the harm caused and the blindness of the human race in connecting the harm with chemistry.

Point number one :- In 2022 researchers in the university of Pennsylvania USA were doing research into the lack of fondness for exercise in some laboratory mice. After eliminating genetics and other variations, they focussed on the gut bacteria of the mice. Hence they discovered that the lazy mice had a depleted intestinal flora (gut biome). To confirm this assumption they killed off the entire gut bacteria of some mice using anti-biotics. Those mice became lazy.

It is not the gut biome or the lazy mice I wish to focus on here, it is the anti-biotics. The above confirms that medical people know that the use of modern drugs such as anti-biotics will damage or kill bacteria in the gut. In my paper UKCDE mentioned on page 1 above, it is clear that the human immune system depends on the good bacteria in the gut for 70% to 80% of its efficacy. Without an effective immune system we become very sick. There are many herbs which act as powerful anti-biotics.

Point number two :- Early in the first half of the 20th century the need for refrigeration increased due to the storage or transport needs of perishable foods; and many other commercial operations. Clever scientists developed in their laboratories a complex unnatural chemical called chlorofluorocarbon (CFC); which because of its low

reactive characteristic was ideal for use in refrigerators. CFC is a gas and when released into the atmosphere has a very long life, maybe 100 years before it depletes and becomes harmless. Here I am focussing on the inability to foresee consequences, not on the gas.

In the second half of the 20th century it was discovered that CFC gas was accumulating in the polar regions and having a significant effect on the ozone (O³) layer in the earth's upper atmosphere, causing a large hole to appear in it. It was also known that the ozone layer was important to organic life on earth, as it contributes significantly to the reduction of harmful radiation from the sun. This radiation can seriously affect organic life on the planet. Hence, after much debate, the Montreal Protocol brought in a phased ban on the use and manufacture of CFC's for all countries; so as to protect organic life on the planet. This ban has been partly effective as the ozone hole has shrunk, due to the use of CFC's now being far less than before. It took many decades for this mistake to be discovered. This is part of the blindness of the human scientific part of the human race.

This second point is no different to the mistake of producing in laboratories medicines in the form of alien chemistry. And then administering them to human beings for health reasons. Scientists who think they are clever are not aware of all the facts about the nature of the human body. Hence they have not considered that alien chemical poisons should not be introduced into the human organism. How many decades will it be before those in the health services realise the mistake of using unnatural chemical poisons as medicines. We need to join up the dots as we have done with CFS's and begin the process of banning the production and use of pharmaceuticals which have any harmful side effects.

But as with the CFC's many make big money from supplying them even today. There are those called collectively "Big Pharma" who will seek to retain their huge profits from being earned by producing medications. Hence we need to be firm and realise that natural plant medicines do not harm the human metabolism for a very good reason. Mother Nature, and herbalists, know which chemistry is harmless, it seems our scientists do not. Clinical trials on pharmaceuticals show many symptoms and side effects. Yet the chemistry is still sold to health systems even though they know it is potentially dangerous. Herbalists would never give a remedy which has the potential to harm a patient.

Concluding Remarks

My message in this paper is of global significance. Since 2020 we have all been affected by a virulent pandemic. The official death toll is fast approaching seven million people across the world; in three years. This pandemic has been the focus of huge human cost, effort and involvement; mostly centred on preventing deaths from the virus.

It is inconsistent that the world has not similarly focussed on the deaths caused by the administration of modern pharmaceuticals. These have been proved to be poisons. It is also proved that they kill many tens of thousands of people every year in the UK alone.

The UK has less than 1% of the world's population. If the deaths due to pharmaceutical medicines in the rest of the world are anywhere near those in the UK, then deaths from medications over three years could easily equal those of the pandemic. And this is only going to get worse unless something is done about pharmaceutical poisons.

My question is simple:- how long will it take the sleepy world to wake up to the fact that modern alien chemistry should not be administered to the human organism, unless it has no side effects at all, as we did with the use of CFC's. And that fully independent clinical checks must be made on all medicines produced in laboratories or commercially produced. Any medication with any adverse effects on human beings, however slight, should not be allowed a licence for use.

We must stop killing patients with medicines.

This is what "**First do no harm**" means.

Appendix – Relevant Extracts From Official Reports in the Paper

“UK Covid-19 Deaths in the Elderly”

From page 4

In October 2019 the House of Lords in the UK debated the effect of taking too many modern medicines; in some cases more than five types of medicine. It was stated that a single modern drug would be tested on younger people, perhaps with one ailment only. The effect of the same dose on older people, who may have multiple ailments, is not known or tested. That same committee reported that nearly 7% of all hospital admissions in the UK had been due to adverse reactions from taking modern drugs (side effects). There are 6.5 million emergency admission annually in England (NHS data); 7% of this figure is 455,000 per year (37,916 per month). Here we have a clue as to how it can be that so many older people in the UK have suffered badly from the covid-19 infection. Is the UK's NHS not such a good thing for older people where medications are concerned?

From page 5

In the October 2019 House of Lords debate cited above, it was also stated that the GPs (medical practitioners) of the population were not fully informed on the effect of multiple medications on their patients. Multiple side effects can produce a worse state of health than the illnesses which they attempted to alleviate. During the debate Prof. Miles Witham, of the University of Newcastle stated :-

“Historically the NHS has been designed, or has evolved, to deal with single problems in single organ systems, and has evolved really to deal with episodic care,” he also said. “It is less good and less well designed at dealing with chronic care and it is particularly poorly equipped to deal with multiple problems affecting a single person.”

Also at the same debate Sir Munir Pirmohamed, the professor of molecular and clinical pharmacology at Liverpool University, said that most of his patients are on more than 10 and often more than 20 drugs. Also he said :-

“Those drugs are used at conventional doses and those doses have been tested in younger populations who had exclusion criteria for trials – so they have been tested in people who don't have the multiple diseases. So when we use a drug at a dose which is licensed at the moment, we are often ‘poisoning’ the elderly because of the dosing that we are using.”

This poisoning would also be poison for the bacteria in the gut.

From page 5

In August 2019 the charity Age UK in their report called "More Harm Than Good", recommended to the UK government that older people who were taking numerous medicines should have their situation reviewed so as to try and reduce the number of medications they were taking. Their research stated that nearly 2 million older people were taking 7 or more prescription medications daily, or more than 4 million taking 5 or less per day; and that they were at risk of severe side effects (this number is more than 50% of the over 60s population of the UK). Older person's health was being seriously affected by the combined effect of too many medications. In some cases death had resulted directly from the side effects of too many medicines; some of which were not really needed or were over-prescribed. In the above Age UK report it was stated :-

"Adverse drug reactions can have severe consequences for older people and cause nearly 6 percent of unplanned hospital admissions. Between 2008 and 2015 the number of emergency hospital admissions caused by adverse drug reactions increased by 53 percent. In 1 in 50 cases that reaction proved to be fatal."

From page 5

Further to the above, in January 2020 the BBC made a "Freedom of Information Request" about the compensation paid out by the NHS in 2019. The figures showed that the NHS was in debt for about UK £4,000,000,000 (four billion pounds sterling) of legal fees. But it also showed that the NHS had paid out UK £83,000,000,000 (83 billion pounds sterling) in compensation claims for negligence (medical mistakes).

From page 6

Breaking News :- On the 13th June 2020 Medscape published on the internet news taken from the British Medical Journal, the main points being :-

"More than 237 million medication errors are made all along the care process every year in England alone, estimated to cost the NHS at least UK£98 million and contributing to the loss of more than 1,700 lives annually, say UK researchers."

"Rachel Ann Elliott, PhD, professor in health economics, Manchester Centre for Health Economics, University of Manchester, and colleagues used a range of sources to examine the adverse drug event (ADE) rate in primary and secondary care, and in care homes."

"---25% of errors having the potential to cause moderate harm and only 2% potentially resulting in serious harm."

This shows us many things. Firstly that the findings of the Universities of Manchester, Sheffield and York in 2017 published in early 2018 (mentioned above), have not been addressed by the UK's NHS system with any success.

From page 9

Research was done by Oxford University for the British Geriatrics Society, into the multiple medication use in the older UK population. They produced their findings in March 2018. Their result showed the following :-

"Medication use, including both prescribed medicines and over the counter products has increased dramatically over the last 2 decades. The number of people taking five or more items quadrupled from 12% to 49%, while the proportion of people who did not take any medication has decreased from around 1 in 5 to 1 in 13."

In a report in the Guardian newspaper on 30th August 2018, where over prescription of medicines in the UK was discussed, Aseem Malhotra stated:-

"The consequences have been devastating. Modern medicine, through over prescription, represents a major threat to public health. Peter Gøtzsche, co-founder of the reputed Cochrane Collaboration, estimates that prescribed medication is the third most common cause of death globally after heart disease and cancer. In the UK, use of prescription drugs is at an all-time high, with almost half of adults on at least one drug and a quarter on at least three – an increase of 47% in the past decade. It's instructive to note that life expectancy in the UK has stalled since 2010, the slowdown being one of the most significant in the world's leading economies."

Is the UK's NHS killing more people than it saves? Will we ever know?

From page 11

At the time of preparing this paper (2020) nearly 42,000 deaths had occurred due to covid-19 in the UK NHS system. Around 82% of these were what was termed "elderly" which probably means over 60 years. The over 60s in the UK comprise 18% of the population. This means the disproportionate ratio in the elderly is more than 4.0 for deaths due to covid-19. This cannot be explained nor proved that their age was the main factor in the increase in deaths of the elderly. There is evidence arising from blood tests which is showing that those who died had a severely reduced number of immune system T cells in their blood. The researchers are blaming the covid-19 virus for causing this reduction. But as this paper shows, the most likely cause is a catalogue of poor diet, poor health and a compromised immune system from too many medications or from medication errors. Meaning that they arrived into hospital with a reduced number of T cells from the start and a weakened state of health due to medication errors.

From page 14

In a report of the British Pharmaceutical Industry on CPD for GPs it is stated:-

"Opponents of industry sponsorship of doctors' CPD argue that there is an inevitable conflict of interest, and that activities are undertaken purely to promote the sales of a company's own products. The heavy investment by pharmaceutical companies may also discourage doctors from considering non-pharmaceutical interventions. Alternative models could be envisaged in which CPD is financed directly by doctors, through their employer, the NHS, or through an independent body funded by industry. In the USA, for example, the pharmaceutical industry cannot contribute directly to continuing medical education."

The term "non-pharmaceutical interventions" actually means the use of natural cures.

Also from page 14 - who are the real quacks?

It is true that in the 19th century in the UK there were many false doctors who would advertise wonder cures and dupe unsuspecting public by their concoctions. Many of these were bogus claims and some resulted in harm to patients. They were not interested in the health of the public but only in getting their money. These false doctors were given the name "quacks". (1) They gave medications which were supposed to cure people. (2) In many cases the medicines caused harm to their patients. (3) They were mainly interested in the money. Eventually their medicines were banned or exposed as being false.

Being as we now know that many of the products from 'big pharma' actually kill people and hence do not cure them, we need to ask are 'big pharmas' the 21st century "Quacks"? (1) They give medications which are supposed to cure people. (2) In many cases the medicines caused harm to their patients. (3) They were mainly interested in the money. If it looks like a duck and quacks like a duck then it is probably a duck. Quack! Quack!